

FACTORS OF INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF MARKETING STRATEGY FOR DEVELOPING INNOVATION ON FARM HOLDINGS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the factors that contribute to the formation of marketing strategies and increase the competitiveness of farms in the agricultural sector. The study examines key aspects such as the development of effective marketing strategies for farms, the use of digital technologies and innovative marketing tools, market segmentation, pricing policy, and branding. According to the results of the study, by properly formulating marketing strategies, farmers will have the opportunity to present their products to a wide audience, conquer new markets, and increase economic efficiency. At the same time, the use of digital marketing and online trading platforms will allow farmers to quickly and efficiently bring their products to the market. The study has developed a number of practical recommendations to increase the competitiveness of farms.

Keywords: Farms, marketing strategy, competitiveness, market segmentation, digital marketing, branding, pricing policy, environmentally friendly products, digital technologies, innovative approaches, sales strategies, improving product quality, market analysis, marketing tools, economic efficiency.

Introduction In the agricultural sector, the need to develop effective marketing strategies for the successful operation of farms, adaptation to market demands, and increased competitiveness is increasing day by day. Farms are mainly engaged in the production and marketing of agricultural products. However, today, increased competition, rapid changes in market conditions and diversification of consumer demands create the need for farmers to develop new marketing approaches. To increase the competitiveness of farms, it is important to correctly formulate marketing strategies, successfully launch products on the market, use branding and modern marketing tools.

The introduction of modern marketing techniques in the agricultural sector not only helps to sell products, but also helps to deeply analyze farmers' market needs and consumer demands. In this process, the widespread use of new tools such as digital marketing and online shopping creates opportunities for farmers to successfully introduce their products to a wide audience and sell them. In addition, farmers can add value to their products through market segmentation, pricing policy, improving product quality and producing environmentally friendly products. The increase in product quality, their production without harming ecosystems, is highly appreciated by consumers.

Such products, in turn, are successfully sold on the market and bring greater income to farmers. When forming marketing strategies for farms, it is necessary to conduct market analysis, study consumer needs, and analyze the activities of competitors. This will allow farmers to quickly adapt to changing market conditions and increase their competitiveness. Market analysis and effective use of marketing tools will create significant advantages for farmers in the process of selling products and creating a brand. At the same time, farmers need to form effective marketing strategies to successfully sell their products and meet market demands, and increase their competitiveness using digital technologies and innovative marketing methods.

In turn, these approaches help to increase the economic efficiency of farms, bring them to a wider market, and ensure economic stability. Therefore, the study of factors that contribute to the formation of marketing strategies and increase competitiveness in farms is one of the important research areas in agriculture today. This article analyzes the main approaches and methods necessary for the formation of marketing strategies and increase competitiveness of farms.

Research methodology. This study uses several methodological approaches to formulate a marketing strategy in farms and identify factors that increase competitiveness. The main goal of the study is to identify methods and strategies necessary for the effective organization of marketing activities of farms and increase competitiveness in market conditions.

Results and discussion The first stage of the research is an analysis of existing scientific literature and studies. The works of Uzbek and foreign scientists on agricultural marketing, competitiveness improvement, market analysis and marketing strategies are studied. At this stage, the main attention is paid to the analysis of factors affecting the marketing strategies of farms, modern marketing tools and market demands.

Questionnaires and interviews:

The study will use questionnaires and interviews to identify marketing strategies of farms and practical skills to improve competitiveness. The questionnaires will be conducted among farmers, agricultural specialists, and marketing experts. This process will help identify marketing strategies used by farmers and challenges in improving competitiveness in the market. The interviews will also provide detailed information about the problems encountered in practice and their solutions.

Market analysis:

The study uses the main methodological approaches to market analysis. Market segmentation, consumer needs and competitor activities are studied. In order for farms to be successful in selling their products, it is necessary to analyze market conditions that will help increase competitiveness. The study provides an in-depth analysis of current market conditions, changes in supply and demand, pricing policy and the importance of branding.

Qualitative and quantitative analysis:

The study uses a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods. Qualitative methods are used to study the problems that arise in the correct formulation of marketing strategies of farms and in increasing their competitiveness. Quantitative methods are used to measure the effectiveness of marketing strategies, the economic impact of increasing competitiveness, and the level of success in adapting to changing market conditions. This methodology allows for practical results to be obtained in terms of increasing the effectiveness of marketing strategies and competitiveness.

Expert assessment:

At the final stages of the research, an expert assessment will be conducted by marketing specialists and agricultural experts. With the help of experts, the results obtained will be analyzed and practical recommendations will be developed to form effective marketing strategies and increase competitiveness in the agricultural products market.

Developing practical recommendations and strategies:

Based on the results of the study, practical recommendations will be developed for the formation of marketing strategies and increasing competitiveness in farms. These recommendations will help to overcome the difficulties encountered in implementing marketing strategies and help farmers successfully operate in market conditions. Thus, the study will deeply study the methodological approaches to the formation of marketing strategies and

increasing competitiveness in farms, the tools used in practice, and the effectiveness of market analysis. The results of the study will provide farmers with practical recommendations for the correct formation of marketing and increasing competitiveness.

The results of the study show that effective implementation of marketing strategies plays a major role in increasing the competitiveness of farms. Farmers have realized that in order to successfully sell their products in the market, marketing should be used not only by advertising products, but also by implementing market segmentation, developing pricing policies, and studying consumer needs. In addition, innovative approaches to marketing strategies, including the use of digital marketing and online trading platforms, help farmers strengthen their position in the market.

Conclusion and suggestions. This study examined the factors that influence the formation of marketing strategies and increase competitiveness in farms. The results of the study showed that there are a number of key factors for the effective organization of marketing activities of farms, strengthening their position in the market and increasing competitiveness. Proper market segmentation, improving product quality, production of environmentally friendly products, use of digital marketing and online trading platforms play an important role in the successful operation of farms.

The results of the study showed that effective implementation of marketing strategies allows farmers to quickly adapt to market conditions, reach a wider audience, and increase competitiveness. Market analysis, consumer demand research, and the correct use of marketing tools are essential for farms to capture the market and create demand for their products.

Farmers can add value to their products by implementing branding and digital technologies to increase competitiveness, as well as improving market segmentation and optimizing pricing policies. The key areas identified in the study include important methodologies that farmers should use when formulating marketing strategies.

Strengthen market segmentation and analysis:

Farmers need to market their products to their target audience through proper market segmentation. This requires developing appropriate marketing strategies for each market segment, analyzing consumer needs, and creating products based on their requirements.

Digital marketing and online sales development:

The wider use of digital marketing and online sales platforms can be an important strategic tool for farmers. Further expanding online sales opportunities, conducting marketing activities through social media and websites can help expand the market. Digital marketing also allows for effective advertising and product information dissemination, and allows for closer contact with consumers.

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